

Carotid Body Tumor (Shamblin Type I): Case Report and Literature Review

Jorge Andrés Myers Esmenjaud¹, Ethel Cassandra Ramírez Ortiz², Francisco Javier Ochoa Carrillo³, Vincenzo Aiello Crocifoglio⁴, Armando López Ortiz⁵

¹Cirugía General Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal, México.

²Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey campus Monterrey, México.

³Cirugía Oncológica Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal, México.

⁴Cirugía Oncológica Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal, México.

⁵Imagenología y Radiología Diagnóstica y Terapéutica Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal, México.

ABSTRACT

Background: Carotid body tumors (paragangliomas of the carotid body) are rare, highly vascularized, slow-growing neoplasms, representing the most common head and neck paraganglioma. Surgical management depends on the Shamblin classification, with type I tumors associated with the lowest complexity and risk.

Objective: To report a case of Shamblin type I carotid body tumor successfully managed surgically with favorable outcomes.

Case Presentation: A 52-year-old woman presented with a painless, pulsatile left lateral neck mass of one-year duration following an upper respiratory infection, positive Fontaine sign, and no compressive symptoms. Doppler ultrasound and CT angiography confirmed a well-defined, highly vascular lesion <4 cm at the left carotid bifurcation, classified as Shamblin type I. Complete resection was performed via subadventitial dissection under general anesthesia, preserving cranial nerves IX, X, and the posterior auricular branch, with LigaSure®-assisted vascular sealing. Operative time was 4 hours, with 300 cc estimated blood loss and no intraoperative complications or need for vascular reconstruction.

Results: Macroscopically, the specimen was a firm, well-encapsulated brown mass. Microscopically, it showed classic paraganglioma features: Zellballen pattern with nests of chief (type I) and sustentacular (type II) cells separated by thin fibrovascular septa, and prominent hypervascularity, confirming the diagnosis.

Conclusion: Early surgical resection in Shamblin type I carotid body tumors yields excellent results with minimal morbidity, neurovascular preservation, and low blood loss. This case supports surgery as the treatment of choice for early-stage lesions, with long-term follow-up recommended to monitor for rare recurrence.

KEYWORDS: Carotid Body Tumor, Paraganglioma, Shamblin Classification, Subadventitial Dissection, Surgical Resection.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
09 April 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Paragangliomas are rare neuroendocrine tumors that arise from extra-adrenal autonomic ganglia. They can be sympathetic (catecholamine-secreting) and typically located in the paravertebral ganglia of the thorax, abdomen, and pelvis; or parasympathetic (nonfunctional) and generally

located along the glossopharyngeal and vagus nerves in the neck and skull base (1).

The carotid body tumor is an ectoderm-derived neoplasm that can be classified as chromaffin (capable of secreting catecholamines) or non-chromaffin. Chromaffin paragangliomas are extremely rare, with an incidence of 0.03% (2).

Carotid Body Tumor (Shamblin Type I): Case Report and Literature Review

Among non-chromaffin paragangliomas in the head and neck, the most common is the chemodectoma or carotid body glomus tumor, which arises in the carotid body and accounts for approximately 65% of all paragangliomas. The carotid body is a chemoreceptor located beneath the adventitia at the bifurcation of the common carotid artery, more specifically on its posteromedial aspect. Notably, these tumors are highly vascularized (3).

In the head and neck region, paragangliomas originate at various distinct anatomic sites. Examples include:

- The carotid body tumor (at the carotid bifurcation),
- Glomus jugulare (at the superior vagal ganglion),
- Glomus tympanicum (along the auricular branch of the vagus nerve),
- Glomus vagale (at the inferior vagal ganglion).

Figure 1. A) Doppler ultrasound: High-velocity arterial flow. B) Carotid body glomus tumor with measurements of 3.39 × 2.62 cm. C) CT angiography: Shamblin type I.

Recent literature has adopted the term temporal bone paraganglioma as a collective designation for tumors originating from the tympanic branch of the glossopharyngeal nerve and the auricular branch of the vagus nerve, previously known primarily as glomus tympanicum (12).

The annual incidence of paragangliomas/pheochromocytomas ranges from 0.8 to 3 per 100,000 individuals (5). Most paragangliomas are diagnosed between the third and fifth decades of life. The male-to-female ratio is approximately equal in patients with hereditary paragangliomas, whereas sporadic tumors are more common in women (6).

In Latin America, the male-to-female ratio is 1:11. In Mexico City, the Hospital de Oncología CMN Siglo XXI reported 98 cases over 20 years, the Hospital de Especialidades CMN Siglo XXI reported 92 cases over 25 years, and INCAN reported 66 cases over 20 years (2).

There are hereditary syndromes associated with the development of paragangliomas. Four genetic syndromes are known: multiple endocrine neoplasia type 2A and 2B, neurofibromatosis type 1, von Hippel-Lindau syndrome, and Carney-Stratakis syndrome.

Another risk factor implicated in the development of carotid body tumors is chronic hypoxia, particularly in individuals living in cities at higher altitudes above sea level (1500 m) and

those with obstructive pulmonary diseases, which leads to hypertrophy of the carotid body (2) (8).

To assess the risk of potential vascular complications related to resection of carotid body tumors, Shamblin et al. (9) proposed a classification scale for these tumors based on conventional angiography or CT/MRI. Three groups are described according to tumor size, relationship to the carotid bifurcation, and adjacent structures (10):

- Type I: small tumors (<4 cm). This is the least frequent (10).
- Type II: medium-sized tumors (>4 cm). They surround the internal or external carotid artery without fully encasing it and are more adherent to the adventitia. A dissection plane exists between the tumor and the vessel. This is the most common type, accounting for

approximately 50% of cases (10).

- Type III: voluminous tumors that encase the carotid arteries. Their excision may require resection of the external carotid artery or even the internal carotid artery, with interposition of a prosthesis or venous graft in the internal carotid artery, leading to higher complication rates. This corresponds to more than 25% of cases (10).

In terms of clinical presentation, the most characteristic finding is a pulsatile lateral cervical mass, generally asymptomatic and slow-growing. The Reclus-Chevassu sign may be present, consisting of a systolic bruit without thrill. The Fontaine sign is also notable, consisting of the tumor being displaceable horizontally but not vertically, which is the main distinguishing feature (10).

For initial diagnosis, Doppler ultrasound is performed, revealing a highly vascularized, well-delimited, hypoechoic mass at the carotid bifurcation. Doppler evaluation shows high-velocity, low-resistance arterial flow (indicating vascular supply primarily from the external carotid artery) (10).

Computed tomography is useful for delineating the tumor's relationships with neighboring structures and assessing its extension; a homogeneous lesion in the infrahyoid space with notable contrast enhancement may be observed (10).

However, for carotid body paragangliomas, CT angiography provides better visualization, enabling improved surgical planning (10).

Carotid Body Tumor (Shamblin Type I): Case Report and Literature Review

There are two treatment modalities. The first involves preoperative embolization of the lesion to reduce tumor size and intraoperative bleeding; however, this is performed only when surgery can be carried out immediately afterward (10). Currently, tumor excision is performed using the subadventitial dissection technique described by Gordon and Taylor, which facilitates a cleavage plane between the vessels and the tumor, along with careful exposure of the bifurcation and carotid vessels. This approach is feasible for Shamblin categories I and II (11).

For tumors classified as Shamblin III, the technique becomes significantly more difficult due to the high probability of injury to neural structures, and vascular grafts may occasionally be required.

Two main complications can occur during resection surgery for carotid body tumors: bleeding and nerve injury.

II. CASE REPORT

A 52-year-old female patient is presented with a surgical history of tonsillectomy, cholecystectomy, one cesarean section, and bilateral tubal occlusion. She reported the onset of her current condition one year prior, describing the sensation of a mass in the left side of the neck following an upper respiratory tract infection. The neck mass was painless and did not cause digestive or respiratory symptoms.

On physical examination, she was normotensive, with mildly elevated heart rate and respiratory rate within normal ranges, oxygen saturation of 95%, and temperature of 37.1 °C. Neurologically intact and oriented, with pale skin and dry mucous membranes. The neck showed a painless mass in the jugulodigastric region protruding anterior to the left sternocleidomastoid muscle border, without apparent bruit or thrill, and with a positive Fontaine sign. The thorax was symmetric, with no respiratory or cardiopulmonary findings.

Weight: 65 kg, height: 162 cm, body mass index (BMI): 24.8 kg/m².

Laboratory studies, including complete blood count and blood chemistry, were within normal ranges. Diagnostic imaging included neck ultrasound and CT angiography (Fig.1), which revealed a tumor at the left carotid bifurcation measuring less than 4 cm. Consequently, the patient was classified as Shamblin type I.

The patient underwent surgical resection of the left carotid body tumor using subadventitial dissection technique under general anesthesia (Fig. 2). Dissection of the adventitia surrounding the tumor was performed, with ligation and division of nutrient vessels until complete tumor resection was achieved, preserving the integrity of cranial nerves IX, X, and the posterior auricular branch. The tumor was intraoperatively confirmed as Shamblin type I. Additionally, resection of jugulodigastric and mid-jugular lymphadenopathy was carried out. Electrosurgical energy with LigaSure® was used for vascular sealing (Fig. 2), thereby reducing operative time and blood loss. Potato starch hemostatic agent was applied, a Biovac #7 drain was placed in the surgical bed, and closure was performed in layers.

The surgery lasted 4 hours, with a total blood loss of 300 cc. The surgical specimen was sent for histopathological examination.

III. RESULTS

The case involved a 52-year-old female patient diagnosed with a left carotid body tumor, preoperatively classified as Shamblin type I based on neck Doppler ultrasound and CT angiography, which revealed a lesion measuring less than 4 cm at the left carotid bifurcation, highly vascularized and well-delimited.

Figure 2. A) The glomus tumor is observed at the bifurcation of the left carotid artery. B) Resection of the paraganglioma using LigaSure. C) Complete resection of the carotid body tumor.

The surgical intervention consisted of complete tumor resection using the subadventitial dissection technique (Gordon and Taylor) under general anesthesia. Relevant cranial nerves (IX, X, and the posterior auricular branch of the vagus) were identified and their integrity preserved. Tumor nutrient vessels were progressively ligated and divided, employing LigaSure® electrosurgical energy for vascular sealing, which helped minimize operative time and intraoperative blood loss. Additionally, resection of jugulodigastric and midjugular lymphadenopathy was

performed. Local potato starch hemostatic agent was applied, a Biovac #7 drain was placed in the surgical bed, and layered closure was carried out.

The total procedure duration was 4 hours, with an estimated blood loss of 300 cc, without the need for transfusions or vascular reconstruction. Intraoperatively, the tumor was confirmed as Shamblin type I, consistent with preoperative findings.

Carotid Body Tumor (Shamblin Type I): Case Report and Literature Review

No intraoperative or immediate postoperative complications occurred, such as significant bleeding, cranial nerve injury, cerebrovascular event, or hemodynamic instability.

Histopathological examination of the surgical specimen revealed, macroscopically, a firm, wellencapsulated brown mass.

Microscopically, characteristic features of a paraganglioma were observed (Fig. 3), including the classic “Zellballen” pattern: nests of cells organized in clusters separated by thin fibrovascular septa. Chief cells (type I), sustentacular cells (type II), and prominent hypervascularity were identified, confirming the definitive diagnosis of carotid body paraganglioma.

Compared with the literature, Shamblin type I tumors, such as the present case, are associated with lower surgical complexity, reduced blood loss volume (generally <500 cc in reported series), and minimal risk of nerve or vascular injury (cranial nerve injury rates <5-10% in type I, versus >20-40% in types II-III). The immediate postoperative course was satisfactory, with no signs of neurological or hemorrhagic morbidity.

Figure 3. A) Classic “Zellballen” pattern: nests of cells organized in clusters separated by thin fibrovascular septa. B) Prominent hypervascularity.

The Shamblin classification remains the standard for predicting surgical complexity and risk of complications. Type I tumors, such as the one in this patient (<4 cm, without significant encasement of the carotid arteries), are associated with lower technical difficulty, minimal intraoperative bleeding, and very low risk of nerve or vascular injury. Metaanalyses and large series report permanent cranial nerve injury rates in type I tumors below 5–10%, mean blood loss <300–500 cc, and perioperative stroke rates around 1–2%—figures markedly lower than those observed in type II (10–20% nerve injury, higher bleeding) and type III (>20–40% nerve injury, up to 4% stroke, and frequent need for vascular reconstruction).

In the present case, complete resection was achieved using subadventitial dissection (Gordon and Taylor technique), with full preservation of cranial nerves IX, X, and the posterior auricular branch, without requiring preoperative embolization, external/internal carotid ligation, or vascular reconstruction. Intraoperative blood loss was only 300 cc,

This case illustrates successful management of an early-stage (Shamblin I) carotid body paraganglioma, with preservation of neurovascular structures, favorable outcomes in terms of surgical safety and efficacy, and classic histopathological confirmation.

IV. DISCUSSION

The carotid body tumor (CBT), also known as carotid body paraganglioma or chemodectoma, is the most common paraganglioma in the head and neck region, accounting for approximately 65% of these tumors. As described in the literature, these tumors are highly vascularized, slow-growing, and generally benign, although they may be associated with hereditary syndromes or factors such as chronic hypoxia at high altitudes. In our case, the 52-year-old patient presented with an asymptomatic, pulsatile lateral cervical mass of recent onset and a positive Fontaine sign—classic findings that guided the diagnosis toward a sporadic CBT.

with an operative time of 4 hours. The use of LigaSure® facilitated efficient vascular sealing, reducing both operative time and hemorrhage, as reported in recent experiences with advanced energy devices. No intraoperative or immediate postoperative complications (bleeding, cranial nerve injury, stroke, or hematoma) were observed, which aligns with the favorable outcomes reported for Shamblin type I tumors in Mexican and Latin American series, where morbidity remains low when intervention occurs at early stages.

Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis with typical macro- and microscopic findings: a firm, wellencapsulated brown mass, “Zellballen” pattern with nests of chief (type I) and sustentacular (type II) cells separated by thin fibrovascular septa, and prominent hypervascularity. These features are pathognomonic of paraganglioma and rule out malignancy in this case, although longterm follow-up is recommended due to the low but existing risk of recurrence (generally <5% after complete R0 resection) or multicentricity.

Carotid Body Tumor (Shamblin Type I): Case Report and Literature Review

Compared with larger series and metaanalyses involving thousands of patients— where the overall cranial nerve injury rate is ~25% and stroke ~3–4%—our result underscores the importance of early diagnosis and surgery for small tumors (Shamblin type I). Factors such as the absence of preoperative embolization did not negatively impact the outcome, consistent with recent evidence questioning its routine benefit in type I–II tumors and reserving it for more voluminous or highly vascularized lesions.

V. CONCLUSION

This case illustrates a successful and complication-free surgical management of a Shamblin type I carotid body tumor in a 52-year-old female patient. Complete resection using the subadventitial technique allowed preservation of neurovascular structures, with low blood loss (300 cc), an operative duration of 4 hours, and typical histopathological confirmation of paraganglioma (Zellballen pattern).

The favorable outcomes, with no postoperative morbidity, reinforce that early surgery for small tumors is safe and effective, carrying minimal risks compared to advanced stages. Long-term follow-up is recommended due to the possibility of recurrence, although this is infrequent after complete resections.

This report highlights the importance of early diagnosis and timely intervention in these rare tumors to achieve excellent functional and oncologic results.

REFERENCES

- I. Pathology and Genetics of Tumours of the Endocrine Organs. WHO Classification of Tumours, DeLellis RA, Lloyd RV, Heitz PU, Eng C (Eds), IARC press, Lyon, France 2004.
- II. M.E. Enríquez-Vega, et al.: Mutación SDHD en tumor de cuerpo carotídeo. *Cirugía y Cirujanos* 2018;86
- III. Shamblin WR, ReMine WH, Sheps SG, Harrison EG. Carotid body tumor (chemodectoma). Clinicopathologic analysis of ninety cases. *Am J Surg.*1971;122:732-9.
- IV. SKANDALAKIS. Surgical Anatomy Medline ® Abstract for Reference 19 of 'Paragangliomas: Epidemiology, clinical presentation, diagnosis, and histology.
- V. Malignant head and neck paragangliomas in SDHB mutation carriers. Boedeker CC, Neumann HP, Maier W, Bausch B, Schipper J, Ridder GJ *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2007;137(1):126.
- VI. Mutations in SDHD, a mitochondrial complex II gene, in hereditary paraganglioma. Baysal BE, Ferrell RE, Willett-Brozick JE, Lawrence EC, Myssiorek D, Bosch A, van der Mey A, Taschner PE, Rubinstein WS, Myers EN, Richard CW 3rd, Cornelisse CJ, Devilee P, Devlin B. *Science.* 2000;287(5454):848.
- VII. Carotid body tumors in inhabitants of altitudes higher than 2000 meters above sea level. Rodríguez-Cuevas S, López-Garza J, Labastida-Almendaro S. *Head Neck.* 1998 Aug;20(5):374-8.
- VIII. Shamblin WR, ReMine WH, Sheps SG, Harrison EG. Carotid body tumor (chemodectoma). Clinicopathologic analysis of ninety cases. *Am J Surg.*1971;122:732-9.
- IX. YANEZ M, RICARDO; LOYOLA B, FRANCISCO y CORNEJO F, JORGE. Tumor de cuerpo carotídeo. *Rev Chil Cir [online].* 2011, vol.63, n.5 [citado 2019-10-05], pp.513-518. Disponible en: <https://scielo.conicyt.cl/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S071840262011000500013&lng=es&nr m=iso>. ISSN 07184026. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4067/S0718-40262011000500013>.
- X. CACERES, Heidi; SILVA, Sindy; AMARILLA, Rodrigo and LACONICH, Diego. Tumor de glomus carotídeo: Carotid glomus tumor. *Rev. Cir. Parag. [online].* 2014, vol.38, n.1 [cited 2019-10-05], pp.35-37. Available from: <http://scielo.iics.una.py/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S230704202014000100008&lng=en&nr m=iso>. ISSN 2307-0420.
- XI. Matz O, Shermetaro C. Glomus Jugulare. 2026 Jan 31. In: *StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2026 Jan–. PMID: 32809324.*